

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Microplastics analysis: can we carry out a polymeric characterisation of atmospheric aerosol using direct inlet Py-GC/MS?

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Table SM1. List of reagents and solvents used in this work.

Material	Maker, code, purity grade, usage
Polyethylene	Goodfellow ET316031
Polyethylene terephthalate	Goodfellow AM306031
Polytetrafluoroethylene	Goodfellow FP306020
Polyamide 6	Goodfellow AM306055
Polyamide 12	Goodfellow AM376010
Polystyrene	Provided in Sample prep box (CDS Analytical Inc.)
Humic acid	Sigma-Aldrich, technical grade, cod. 53680
Hydrogen Peroxide	Sigma Aldrich, 30%, ACS reagent
<i>n</i> -Hexane	Merck, puriss. p.a., ACS reagent, reag. Ph. Eur., ≥99%
Ethanol	Merck, absolute, for HPLC, ≥99.8%
Methanol	Merck, for HPLC, ≥99.9%

Figure SM1. Visualisations of the sampling site. Images from Google Earth®.

Table SM2. Date and volume of total suspended particulate samples.

Sample number	Sampling date	Volume (m ³)
S1	21-23 July 2021	872
S2	23-26 July 2021	1271
S3	26-28 July 2021	852

Table SM3. AMDIS parameters.

Identification	Minimum factor match	60 %
	Type of analysis	Use retention time
	RT window	0.2 min
	Match factor penalties level	Average
	Maximum penalty	20
Deconvolution	Component width	12
	Adjacent peak subtraction	One
	Resolution	Medium
	Sensitivity	Medium
	Shape requirements	Medium
QA/QC	Solvent tailing	84 m/z
	Column bleed	207 m/z

Figure SM2. Resolution of chromatographic methods calculated using the alkene/alkadiene couples.

C8: 1-Octene/1,7-Octadiene; C9: 1-Nonene/1,8-Nonadiene; C10: 1-Decene/1,9-Decadiene; C11: 1-Undecene/1,10-Undecadiene; C12: 1-Dodecene/1,11-Dodecadiene; C13: 1-Tridecene/1,12-Tridecadiene; C14: 1-Tetradecene/1,13-Tetradecadiene; C15: 1-Pentadecene/1,14-Pentadecadiene; C16: 1-Hexadecene/1,15-Hexadecadiene; C17: 1-Heptadecene/1,16-Heptadecadiene; 1-Octadecene/1,17-Octadecadiene. Program A: 40°C, 2 min, 13°C min⁻¹ to 261°C, 6°C min⁻¹ to 300°C, 2 min. Program B: 50°C, 2 min, 10°C min⁻¹ to 320°C, 3 min. Program C: 40°C, 4 min, 5°C min⁻¹ to 200°C, 10°C min⁻¹ to 300°C.

Table SM4. Identification match and quantitative repeatability for polymer markers.

Polymer	Marker	Identification match (%)	Repeatability (%)	Marker	Identification match (%)	Repeatability (%)
PE	1-Octene	95-100	34	1,7-Octadiene	98-99	91
	1-Nonene	98-100	34	1,8-Nonadiene	72-99	49
	1-Decene	99-100	26	1,9-Decadiene	100	48
	1-Undecene	98-100	27	1,10-Undecadiene	97-100	43
	1-Dodecene	99-100	29	1,11-Dodecadiene	98-100	40
	1-Tridecene	99-100	28	1,12-Tridecadiene	99	38
	1-Tetradecene	100	26	1,13-Tetradecadiene	99	36
	1-Pentadecene	100	26	1,14-Pentadecadiene	98-100	36
	1-Hexadecene	100	40	1,15-Hexadecadiene	98-100	75
	1-Heptadecene	100	26	1,16-Heptadecadiene	97-100	32
	1-Octadecene	100	25	1,17-Octadecadiene	97-100	31
	PET	Benzene	100	57	Benzoic acid	99-100
Acetophenone		100	105	Divinyl terephthalate	97-100	102
Vinyl benzoate		100	80			
PTFE	Tetrafluoroethylene	99-100	53			
PS	Styrene	98-100	26	Styrene dimer	87-100	1
PA6	Caprolactam	97-100	6			
PP	2-Methyl-1-pentene	89-91	37	2,4-Dimethyl-1-heptene	88-89	47
PVC	Chlorobenzene	71-90	57			
PA12	Nonanenitrile	97-100	70	Undecanenitrile	97-100	93
	Decanenitrile	97-100	96	Dodecanenitrile	97-100	20

Table SM5. Polymer detection in the mixture.

Polymer (tracer)	Identification match Test 1 (%)	Identification match Test 2 (%)
PE (alkenes)	66-96	66-91
PE (alkadienes)	70-95	68-94
PTFE (tetrafluoroethylene)	74	-
PA6 (caprolactam)	67	93 (shifted 1.2 min ahead)
PP (2,4-dimethyl-1-heptene)	93	75
PS (styrene dimer)	-	74
PA12 (alkanenitriles)	72 (dodecanenitrile only)	88-90
PVC (chlorobenzene)	-	-

Figure SM3. Humic acid pyrogram, test 1: total ion current (TIC), and extracts of ions m/z 55 and m/z 104, with identification of polymer indicator compounds.

Table SM6. Detected polymer indicator compounds in humic acid.

Marker	Polymer	Identification match Test 1 (%)	Identification match Test 2 (%)	Identification match Test 3 (%)
Tetrafluoroethylene	PTFE	-	90	94
2-Methyl-1-pentene	PP	66	62	63
Benzene	PET/PVC	100	100	100
Toluene	PS/PVC	100	99	100
1-Octene	PE/PA12	85	85	86
Octane	PE	98	98	97
2,4-Dimethyl-1-heptene	PP	70	74	72
1,8-Nonadiene	PE/PA12	-	79	77
1-Nonene	PE/PA12	97	97	97
Nonane	PE	95	98	99
Styrene	PS/PVC	81	-	-
1-Decene	PE/PA12	98	99	99
Decane	PE	-	96	73
Acetophenone	PET	64	64	66
Indene	PVC	100	100	100
1,10-Undecadiene	PE/PA12	-	90	-
1-Undecene	PE/PA12	97	98	98
Undecane	PE	98	97	99
1,11-Dodecadiene	PE	-	91	89
1-Dodecene	PE	97	95	98
Dodecane	PE	94	94	93
1,12-Tridecadiene	PE	78	89	87
1-Tridecene	PE	91	90	92
Tridecane	PE	95	95	95
1-Methyl naphthalene	PVC	96	100	100
1,13-Tetradecadiene	PE	67	87	86
1-Tetradecene	PE	92	97	96
Tetradecane	PE	89	90	94
1,14-Pentadecadiene	PE	75	86	78
1-Pentadecene	PE	95	97	95
Pentadecane	PE	94	91	93
1,15-Hexadecadiene	PE	-	83	77
1-Hexadecene	PE	90	95	95
Hexadecane	PE	88	88	88
1,16-Heptadecadiene	PE	-	75	82
1-Heptadecene	PE	93	95	94
Heptadecane	PE	86	87	87
1,17-Octadecadiene	PE	62	75	66
1-Octadecene	PE	90	92	92
Octadecane	PE	85	87	88

Table SM7. Detected polymer tracers in aerosol samples. For identified alkenes, alkadienes and 2,4-dimethyl-1-heptene, the tracer area to OAB ratio is reported in brackets.

Marker	Polymer	S1, Test 1 match %	S1, Test 2 match %	S1, Test 3 match %	S2, Test 1 match %	S2, Test 2 match %	S2, Test 3 match %	S3, Test 1 match %	S3, Test 2 match %	S3, Test 3 match %
Benzene	PET/PVC	94	93	94	100	94	99	95	96	97
Toluene	PS/PVC	99	98	99	100	99	99	99	97	100
1-Octene	PE/PA12	82 (3.3)	80 (4.7)	82 (3.8)		80 (<1)	83 (<1)	82 (<1)	74 (<1)	72 (<1)
Octane	PE	86	70	69		67				
2,4-Dimethyl-1-heptene	PP	80 (6.2)	79 (7.3)	64 (6.3)					90 (2.1)	
1,8-Nonadiene	PE/PA12	63 (11)	70 (11)	61 (3.4)						
1-Nonene	PE/PA12	96 (3.4)	97 (4.0)	98 (3.3)	82 (<1)	97 (<1)	97 (<1)	95 (<1)	89 (<1)	76 (<1)
Nonane	PE	66	68	67						
Styrene	PS/PVC	98	99	97		89	93	92		
1,9-Decadiene	PE/PA12		63							
1-Decene	PE/PA12	93 (6.0)	94 (6.6)	94 (5.7)		96 (<1)	80 (<1)	96 (<1)	89 (<1)	69 (<1)
Decane	PE	88	76	85			76			
Acetophenone	PET	97	98	93						
Indene	PVC	98	98	98	87	98	97	95		
1-Undecene	PE/PA12	95 (3.5)	96 (4.3)	96 (3.8)	64 (<1)	97 (<1)	97 (<1)	96 (<1)	89 (<1)	74 (<1)
Undecane	PE	87	86	83		71	71			
1,11-Dodecadiene	PE	79 (12)	77 (17)	76 (14)						
Benzoic acid	PET	88	91	84						
1-Dodecene	PE	97 (7.4)	98 (7.5)	98 (8.5)		96 (<1)	96 (<1)	94 (<1)	88 (<1)	83 (<1)
Dodecane	PE	78	79	69		63	80	72	69	
1,12-Tridecadiene	PE		74 (6.8)							
1-Tridecene	PE	96 (3.6)	97 (4.4)	95 (3.5)		95 (<1)	93 (<1)	88 (<1)	75 (<1)	78 (<1)
Tridecane	PE	87	86	92			69			
1-Methyl naphthalene	PVC	95	95	98	69	76	85	75		
1,13-Tetradecadiene	PE	68 (2.9)	63 (3.4)	62 (6.9)						
1-Tetradecene	PE	96 (6.5)	97 (6.5)	97 (7.0)		95 (<1)	96 (<1)	96 (<1)	85 (<1)	
Tetradecane	PE	86	88	86		66	61			
1,14-Pentadecadiene	PE		75 (2.3)	77 (1.8)						
1-Pentadecene	PE	97 (3.8)	96 (4.7)	96 (4.3)		91 (<1)	93 (<1)	92 (<1)	81 (<1)	

Marker	Polymer	S1, Test 1 match %	S1, Test 2 match %	S1, Test 3 match %	S2, Test 1 match %	S2, Test 2 match %	S2, Test 3 match %	S3, Test 1 match %	S3, Test 2 match %	S3, Test 3 match %
Pentadecane	PE	89	86	89	74	74	76	76	76	
1,15-Hexadecadiene	PE	71 (3.9)	77 (5.0)							
1-Hexadecene	PE	93 (3.8)	95 (4.4)	94 (4.1)	88 (<1)	90 (<1)	85 (<1)	64 (<1)		
Hexadecane	PE	77	77	79	61					
Styrene dimer	PS	74	96							
1,16-Heptadecadiene	PE	62 (6.8)								
1-Heptadecene	PE	94 (4.0)	94 (3.9)	95 (3.3)	84 (<1)	87 (<1)	79 (<1)			
Heptadecane	PE	81	71	78		61	63			
1,17-Octadecadiene	PE									
1-Octadecene	PE	92 (4.2)	83 (5.0)	90 (4.0)	80 (<1)	83 (<1)	79 (<1)	71 (<1)		
Octadecane	PE		61	60						
Sty/Tol	PS	1.0	3.4	<1	<1	<1	<1	<1	<1	<1

Table SM8. Detected polymer tracers in dust material (SRM2585), with the analysed quantity on squared brackets. For identified alkenes, alkadienes and 2,4-dimethyl-1-heptene, the tracer area to OAB ratio is reported in round brackets.

Marker	Polymer	Test 1 [1.2 mg] Identification match (%)	Test 2 [1.5 mg] Identification match (%)	Test 3 [2.5 mg] Identification match (%)
Benzene	PET/PVC	93	99	96
Toluene	PS/PVC	99	100	97
1,7-Octadiene	PE/PA12		78 (1.1)	61 (1.6)
1-Octene	PE/PA12	62 (1.9)	79 (1.7)	71 (5.0)
Octane	PE	91	85	61
2,4-Dimethyl-1-heptene	PP	75 (1.8)		73 (7.6)
1,8-Nonadiene	PE/PA12		90 (1.1)	74 (1.2)
1-Nonene	PE/PA12	90 (1.4)	91 (1.2)	89 (2.9)
Nonane	PE	95	93	91
Styrene	PS/PVC	98	98	98
1,9-Decadiene	PE/PA12	81 (4.1)		75 (11)
1-Decene	PE/PA12	97 (2.2)	62 (2.0)	97 (3.4)
Decane	PE	95	94	92
Acetophenone	PET	97	98	95
Indene	PVC	98	100	98
1,10-Undecadiene	PE/PA12			67 (2.6)
1-Undecene	PE/PA12	96 (1.4)	97 (1.2)	99 (3.0)
Undecane	PE	77	93	95
1,11-Dodecadiene	PE	92 (1.4)		75 (2.9)
Nonanenitrile	PA12			86
Benzoic acid	PET			72
1-Dodecene	PE	97 (1.6)	96 (1.5)	95 (3.5)
Dodecane	PE	95	90	93
Caprolattame	PA6	88	87	
1,12-Tridecadiene	PE	82 (2.8)	63 (1.6)	72 (33)
1-Tridecene	PE	95 (1.2)	97 (1.1)	95 (2.7)
Tridecane	PE	94	90	88
1-Methyl naphthalene	PVC	97	97	96
1,13-Tetradecadiene	PE	86 (<1)		85 (5.9)
1-Tetradecene	PE	94 (1.6)	96 (1.4)	90 (3.1)
Tetradecane	PE	96	87	93
1,14-Pentadecadiene	PE	83 (2.0)	72 (<1)	80 (3.7)
1-Pentadecene	PE	96 (1.3)	95 (1.1)	94 (2.9)
Pentadecane	PE	91	72	87
1,15-Hexadecadiene	PE	86 (1.6)		60 (2.3)
1-Hexadecene	PE	95 (1.1)	94 (<1)	95 (2.7)
Hexadecane	PE	83	81	69
1,16-Heptadecadiene	PE	83 (2.3)		69 (3.9)
1-Heptadecene	PE	95 (<1)	92 (<1)	96 (2.1)
Heptadecane	PE	89	82	84
1-Octadecene	PE	96 (1.5)	96 (1.4)	97 (4.0)
Octadecane	PE	67	68	90

Table SM9. Detected polymers by Micro-FTIR in humic acid, SRM2585 and aerosol samples.

		Humic acid	SRM2585	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3
Acrylate urethane				Det		
Acrylic polymer			Det			
Acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene terpolymer	ABS		Det			Det
Ethylene vinyl acetate polymer			Det			
Ethylene-chlorotrifluoroethylene copolymer	ECTFE				Det	Det
Ethylene-methyl acrylate copolymer	EMA			Det		Det
Ethylene-methyl acrylate copolymer with tertiary B				Det		
Ethylene-vinyl acetate copolymer	EVA			Det	Det	Det
High-density polyethylene	HDPE	Det		Det	Det	Det
Low-density polyethylene	LDPE					Det
Modacrylic				Det		
Nitrile-butadiene rubber	NBR			Det		
Nylon 12	PA12		Det	Det	Det	
Nylon 6	PA6	Det	Det	Det	Det	Det
Poly-1-butene						Det
Polyacrylic acid	PAA			Det		
Polyacrylonitrile	PAN			Det		
Polyesters	PES		Det	Det	Det	Det
Polyolephins	PO	Det		Det		Det
Polyphenylene sulfide	PPS				Det	
Polyphthalamide	PPA	Det	Det	Det	Det	Det
Polypropylene	PP		Det			
Polypropylene	PP			Det	Det	Det
Polystyrene	PS	Det		Det		
Polytetrafluoroethylene	PTFE	Det			Det	Det
Polyurethane	PU		Det			
Paraffin/polyethylene wax blend						Det
Semi-Aromatic Polyarylamides	PARA	Det	Det	Det		Det
Styrene-butadiene copolymer			Det			